

Efficacy Of Lecture As A Teaching-Learning Tool For Gaining Knowledge In Anatomy- A Cross-Sectional Study

Dr Rajasri Chunder¹, Dr Sayantani Majumdar², Nabanita Chakraborty³

¹Professor and Head, ²Associate Professor, ³Assistant Professor
Department of Anatomy,

Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Background: Anatomy is the subject which forms the foundation stone of the Medical Education as without the knowledge of the human body all other information is vain. This study helps in obtaining feedback from the 1st Professional MBBS students on their perception of lectures as a mode of teaching for gaining knowledge in Anatomy.

Method: A structured pre-validated questionnaire-based study was conducted at the Department of Anatomy, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Budge Budge. The participants were the 140-2nd year MBBS students of the Academic year 2022-23, who had already cleared the 1st Professional MBBS successfully.

Results: 91.4 % students preferred chalk and board teaching assisted with audiovisual aids as the teaching tool during lecture class. Majority of students preferred a duration 45 minutes for lecture classes. 106 students (75.7%) felt that both Lecture and Dissection/Practical classes together are the best methods to learn Anatomy. Further interpretation of the feedback reflected that the learners still preferred to be taught in a predominantly individualized care-based environment.

Conclusion: Changes in teaching methods and using interactive novel methods may be effective for teaching and learning Anatomy and improving students' attitudes towards the clinical importance of Anatomy. Proper utilization of the 210 hours allocated as lecture hours should be done. It is evident from the feedback, observations and suggestions obtained from the students that they still prefer small group practical/demonstration classes to be taught in an individualized care-based environment which reflects their lack of or incomplete attitudinal shift towards the more institutionalized care-based environment of a medical education institution.

Keywords: medical students; undergraduate teaching; students' feedback evaluation; attitudinal shift, lecture session.

INTRODUCTION

Lecture is an economical and efficient method of conveying information to large groups of students. The lecture can provide an entrée into a difficult topic, it can offer different perspectives on a subject, it can communicate relevant personal, clinical or laboratory experience, and it can deliver a research-based view where teaching is immersed in a research-intensive university. [1] The conventional ways of lectures are however changing, with greater engagement of students during the lecture with use of latest audio-visual techniques and recordings of lectures being made available to students.

Medical Council of India introduced the Competency based Undergraduate Curriculum for the Indian Medical graduate in 2018. In this new curriculum implemented from the Academic year 2019-20 provides an effective outcome-based strategy where various domains of teaching including teaching learning methods and assessment form the framework of competencies. Anatomy has 81 topics with multiple competencies

under each topic. According to the latest Competency Based Medical Education Curriculum (CBME) Regulations published by National Medical Commission Undergraduate Medical Education Board in 2023, a total of 620 hours has been allocated to Anatomy with lecture hours comprising approximately one-third of it i.e. 210 hours. The total duration of the Phase 1 MBBS programme is around 12 months. Hence, judicious and optimum utilization of these teaching hours is of utmost importance for attaining the specified objectives. In this regard, the Department of Anatomy, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, follows a systematic policy for lectures, which involves distribution of each topic according to the guidelines laid down by the MCI in the UG Curriculum, Volume 1 into a requisite number of individual lectures and outlining the specific learning objectives for each of these classes. This system permits the assignment of each lecture to a particular faculty member without the possibility of omission or repetition of any part of the topic, while simultaneously ensuring that any particular section is covered by a group of speakers thus avoiding bias and monotony.

Many faculties are still used to imply reading their own notes when delivering lectures. This format may not be best suitable for the present generation of learners. [2] Now with the gradual introduction of newer techniques like use of multimedia software presentation such as Microsoft power point lectures has become more engaging and helps in better understanding. [3]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

AIM: To study the perception of the students about lecture as a teaching-learning tool for gaining knowledge in Anatomy.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To know the students' preferences regarding the current methods applied in teaching-learning methods of Anatomy
2. To assess their perception of strength and weakness in the present teaching-learning methods.
3. To identify their felt need for modification in the teaching-learning approach.

METHODS

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted in Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Budge Budge, West Bengal after obtaining clearance from the Scientific Research and Ethics committee with a reference no. of . The study population was the third semester medical students of Academic year 2022-23 who had successfully cleared the 1st professional MBBS University examination under WBUHS were selected for the study. A total of 140 respondents were selected after obtaining their informed consent. The participants were also instructed not to provide any personal details like identity, roll number etc. apart from their age, sex in the questionnaire. The questionnaire devised for the present study consisted of ten questions with options given. It was divided into three sections viz. A, B & C. Section A consisted of three questions with answer in 3-point Likert scale. The students were instructed to pick the option to each question which they felt was most appropriate. The Section B comprising of seven questions, where respondents were provided with three to four options and they were encouraged to furnish their independent and unbiased opinion regarding some aspects of the lectures as a effective teaching-learning tool. Lastly in Section C, suggestions for improvement and any other remarks were invited in the questionnaire. The students were discouraged to put in writing any individualized comment about the faculty members or their way of teaching. The completed response sheets were collected, tabulated and statistically analyzed using SPSS software.

RESULTS

Out of the 140 respondents (n= 140), the age distribution were 2.9 % of 18years, 32.9 % of 19 years, 38.6% of 20 years, 14.3% 21years and 11.4% 22years of age. The sex ratio was 37.1% males and 62.9 % females. 94.3% respondents felt that interesting topics were covered during the lecture classes, while 1.4% disagreed to this and 4.3% had no opinion about the same. 126 students (90.0%) students agreed that faculties made the lecture classes interesting while 2 students (1.4%) disagreed and 12 students (8.6%) did not opine. 92.9 % respondents felt that faculties were well versed with using advanced audiovisual aids during lecture classes while none (0%) disagreed and a minor 7.1% had no opinion. **(Fig 1).**

In Section B, three to four options were provided against each question and the respondents were encouraged to furnish their independent and unbiased opinion regarding some aspects of the lectures as a effective teaching-learning tool. Majority of the students – 128 (91.4 %) opined that chalk and board teaching assisted with audiovisual aids is the most preferred teaching tool during lecture class. None (0%) of them were in favor of only audiovisual aids as teaching tool and only 12 (8.6%) preferred only chalk and board (Fig 2A). 84.3 % of the respondents felt that all important parts of the topics are covered during the lecture classes while 7.1% felt that all grey areas are not covered during the lectures. 8.6% felt that unnecessary difficult areas are taught during lecture class made it less interesting (Table 1). 58.6% students felt that the ideal duration of the lectures classes should be 45 minutes, 32.9 % said 60 min while 4.3% were in favor of 30 minute lecture classes (Fig 2B). 58.6% of respondents felt that Dissection classes generated more interest in the subject of Anatomy followed by Self-directed learning at 20.0%. Only 12.9% felt lecture classes generated interest in learning Anatomy (Fig 2C). 106 students (75.7%) felt that both Lecture and Dissection/Practical classes together are the best methods to learn Anatomy, whereas only 30 students (21.4%) thought dissection/practical classes are alone enough for gaining knowledge in Anatomy (Fig 2D). Nearly equal number of respondents felt that the most effective learning method is Lecture (32.9%) and Group discussion (31.4%). (Table 2).

Figure1: showing feedback about the content of lectures and faculty expertise in the conduction of lecture

Fig 2A showing most effective teaching tool in lecture class

Table 1 : showing feedback about content of the lecture classes

<i>Reasons</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Discuss all important topics	118	84.3
All important topics are not covered	10	7.1
Discuss unnecessary difficult topics	12	8.6

Fig 2B showing the students’ feedback about ideal duration of lecture class

Fig 2C- showing percentage of the different methods that generate interest in Anatomy

Fig 2D methods that help in gaining knowledge in Anatomy

Table 2: showing most effective method of learning in Anatomy

<i>Teaching Method</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Normal lectures	46	32.9
Tutorial	10	7.1
Seminar	12	8.6
Group Discussion	44	31.4
One-to-one interaction	26	18.6
Others	2	1.4

DISCUSSION

Since the inception of education either on a professional or social level, didactic lectures have occupied a pivotal position in dissemination of knowledge from the teacher to the student. The entire MBBS curriculum underwent a paradigm shift with the introduction of the National Medical Commission which featured a competency based learning agenda and making the education learner centric rather than teacher centric. Research have shown that didactic lectures in their age-old pattern have been quite an ineffective method of propagation of effective knowledge for which the hours allotted for the same have been reduced in each subject including Anatomy in first year MBBS curriculum. The questionnaire in this study is analyzed based on mainly 2 criteria i.e. teaching methodologies and secondly learning methodologies preferred by the students. In a study conducted by Nagar et al, 54.6% of students liked to get a handout of material before the lecture as compared to 64 % students in the present study who strongly agreed that handout should be given prior to lectures. [4] In a study conducted by Chakravarti et al combined method of teaching which includes old traditional method of teaching and modern computer assisted learning methods was preferred by MBBS students. [5] Similarly in our study, 91.4% students preferred a combination of audiovisual aid assisted teaching along with chalk and board for lecture. Classic chalk and board teaching in lectures was preferred by almost 34 % of students and combined method of teaching i.e. chalk and board and OHP and or LCD was preferred by 56% of students in the study conducted by Yadav et al. [6] In this same study student did not prefer student seminar and tutorials as a part of teaching similar to our study- Seminar- 8.6% and tutorial- 7.1%. In the study by Reenu Kumari et al, 70% of students preferred LCD with chalk and board while only 8 % preferred traditional chalk and board methodology. [7] This is very similar to the finding in the present study where only 12 out of 140 students preferred traditional chalk and board teaching. In the study by Novelli, the fresh 1st year medical students tend to preferred chalk and board method for subjects such as biochemistry and physiology. [8] In blackboard teaching, teacher takes breaks for writing, drawing

and rubbing the board which allow students to follow and grasp the content in better manner. [9] In the study by Reenu Kumari et al about 56% preferred use of 3D models, videos and other audiovisual aids and 22% preferred problem-based learning and only 3 % preferred student seminar. In the present study 91.4 % of students preferred combination of audio-visual aids with blackboard teaching and 48 % preferred problem-based learning and students strongly agreed that group discussion was extremely useful for teaching-learning method. Prasad et al found that there was no significant difference between Powerpoint teaching method and blackboard method. However, subject coverage and demonstration using figures, charts and clinical conditions were better with Powerpoint as compared to blackboard teaching.[10] Regarding the ideal duration of the lectures- 58.6% opined that the ideal duration of lectures is 45 minutes. This finding was similar to the 62% in the study conducted by Kurle et al in the subject of Physiology. [11] Narendran et al[12] studied the perception about conventional one-hour live lectures in clinical topics among sixth semester MBBS students and found that 66.39% of the participants felt the duration of any lecture be kept at a maximum of 30 minutes, 30.33% agreed for 45 minutes while 4 participants (3.28%) preferred a 1-hour lecture on any given topic. Srivastava et al [13] Arora N et al, [14] Larvalmawi F et al [15] and Rani et al, [16] most of the students reported that practical demonstration and practical skill work most helpful methods in learning Anatomy in accordance to our study where 58% found dissection most effective.

There was a limitation of this study. The sample size was small, and our results might have differed with a larger study sample.

CONCLUSION

Out of the total 620 hours of Anatomy during the first-year curriculum as per the GMER 2023, 210 hours are allocated to Lectures. So, effective utilization of these hours is highly recommended for imparting knowledge of Anatomy. Hence, feedback from the students facilitates a change in preconceived notions about teaching learning principles on the part of the faculty. At the same time, it is evident from the feedback, observations and suggestions obtained from the students that they still prefer small group practical/demonstration classes to be taught in an individualized care-based environment which reflects their lack of or incomplete attitudinal shift towards the more institutionalized care-based environment of a medical education institution.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We appreciate the active participation of the second year MBBS students of the academic year 2022-23 of Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Budge Budge, West Bengal to take time from their daily academic schedule to take part in this study.

REFERENCE

- [1] G.Brown, M. Manogue. "Refreshing lecturing: a guide for lecturers." AMEE Medical Education Guide No. 22. Med. Teach, vol. 23, pp-231–244, 2001
- [2] R.F Edlich. "My last lecture." J Emerg Med, 11(6), pp- 771–774, 1993
- [3] D. Oblinger. " Boomers, gen Xers, and millennials: Understanding the "New" students." Educause Review, 38(4) pp- 37-47,2003.
- [4] S.K Nagar, O. Malukar, D Kubavat, V Prajapati, D Ganatra, A Rathwa. (2022). "Students' perception on anatomy teaching methodologies." National Journal of Medical Research, Vol 2(01), pp-111–112,2022
- [5] S Chakrabarti, L.B Shilpakala, G Raghunath, P.K Sankaran. "Teaching and learning perception of anatomy by first MBBS (2014-15) batch students." Indian Journal of Clinical Anatomy and Physiology, Vol. Jan;4(1) pp- 87-91,2017.
- [6] Y Kumari,Yadav, B Singh, M Kaur, R Gupta "Evaluating anatomy teaching methodology as per the percipience of first MBBS students- A questionnaire-based study." International Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Sciences. Vol5, (2) May- Aug pp-240-4, 2015.
- [8] E.L Novelli, A.A Fernandes." Students' preferred teaching techniques for biochemistry in biomedicine and medicine courses." Biochem Mol Biol Educ.; Vol 35, pp-263-6,2007.

- [9] V Seth, P Upadhyaya, M Ahmad, V Kumar. "Impact of various lecture delivery methods in pharmacology." EXCLI J, vol-9, pp- 96-101, 2010
- [10] B.K Prasad, S Prasad. "To Assess the Effect of Teaching by Blackboard and Powerpoint." IJPPR, Human, Vol. 7 (4), pp- 208-214,2016.
- [11] N Narendran, M.S Lally, J Rajany. "Perception of live lectures by medical students." J. Evolution Med. Dent. Sci. vol. 6 (23) pp- 1877,2017
- [12] D.G Kurle, S.G Goyal, S.S Joshi, K.M.N Singh, P.V Sarkate . "Perception of Students and Teachers of a Good Lecture: A Questionnaire-Based Cross-Sectional Study in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital." National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology, Vol 8 (3), pp- 406-41,2017.
- [13] A Srivastava A Singh." Perception and feedback of medical students about teaching methods in Anatomy." Indian Journal of Clinical Anatomy and Physiology, vol 7(1).pp-104-109,2020.
- [14] N Arora, A Kumar. "Student feedback on teaching and evaluation methodology in human anatomy." Int J Med App Sci. vol 3, pp-258–263,2014
- [15] F Lalvarmawi, U Banik, M Devi. "Feedback of medical students on teaching and evaluation methodology in Physiology." Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol, vol 5(1) pp- 36–38, 2015.
- [16] A Rani, J Chopra, R.K Diwan, A.K Pankaj." Students' feedback on the utility of gross anatomy manual in learning anatomy" IJMHS, vol 4 pp-62–63, 2014.